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Level of Distribution of Cashew Gummosis (*Anacardium Occidentale* L.) In Cote D'ivoire

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Abstract:

The Ivorian cashew orchard faces the threat of gummosis. This disease is a fungal epidemic. It has been identified as a real threat to cashew nut production in all producing countries. The aim of this study is to update the distribution map of gummosis in the different agro-ecological zones from 2022 to 2024 in Côte d'Ivoire. To achieve this, surveys were carried out in sixteen (16) cashew-producing regions. Phytopathological assessment focused on disease incidence and severity. Symptomatic bark was also collected for isolation. The disease was present in all the regions visited, with varying levels of infection. The highest incidence rates and severity indices were recorded in the localities of Sambadougou, Tiémé, Kolia and Kasséré. These localities belong to agro-ecological zone VI. The lowest incidence rates were obtained in Gobazra (3%), Bonoufla (3%) and Bonon (4%). These localities belong to agro-ecological zone II. Pathogens isolated from gum blight samples belonged to three genera: Pestalotia, Ceratocystis and Lasiodiplodia.

Key words: Cashew, gummosis, Lasiodiplodia, Ivory Coast

1. INTRODUCTION

Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) is a crowned perennial belonging to the Anacardiaceae family, growing up to 15 metres in height (Nakasone & Paul, 1998). It is the only species of this family that carries economic weight thanks to its edible apple and nutritious kernel, which comes from the drupe (Aliyu, 2012). The cashew nut is one of the most widely traded nuts in the world. In recent years, the bulk of production has come from Africa, particularly West Africa, which alone accounts for 48% of global supply (International Nut and Dried Fruit Council Foundation 2021). Out of an estimated annual world production of 3.85 millions tonnes at the end of the 2021/2022 season ([https : //www.statista.com](https://www.statista.com)), Côte d'Ivoire produced 1,024,000 tonnes of raw cashew nuts. Today in Côte d'Ivoire, cashew cultivation employs more than 420,000 producers and is practised on an area of 1,400,000 hectares, making Côte d'Ivoire the world's

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leading producer and exporter of raw cashew nuts (FIRCA, 2021). However, cashew cultivation is under threat from numerous pests, notably fungal attacks (Banito *et al.*, 2021). Cashew gummosis is much feared in producing countries, as it poses a serious threat to cashew production. It has caused 30% stand losses in some cashew plantations in Brazil (Coutinho *et al.*, 2016). The same disease has unfortunately been identified in cashew groves in Côte d'Ivoire (Soro *et al.* 2017). To date, there has been very little information on this disease. It is in this context that the present study was initiated and aims to provide data that can contribute to decision-making for a better orientation of control actions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study areas

The study was carried out in six agro-ecological zones (ZAE I, ZAE II, ZAE IV, ZAE V, ZAE VI and ZAE VII) due to the presence of cashew orchards in these zones. The vegetation found in ZAE I is dense rainforest, located to the south. The same vegetation is found in ZAE II, to the west. ZAE IV is semi-deciduous dense rainforest. ZAE V is a transitional forest zone. ZAE VI is characterized by humid tropical savannah vegetation. ZAE VII is characterized by dry tropical savannah vegetation (Figure 1) (Halle & Bruzon, 2006).

Figure 1 : Agro-ecological zones in Côte d'Ivoire (Halle & Bruzon, 2006)

2.2 Equipment

The technical field equipment used during the present study consisted of a machete, markers (chalk), 70% alcohol, cotton, data collection sheets, envelopes, a camera and a GPS.

2.3 Methods

2.3.1. Sample collection

The orchards surveyed were identified randomly (Balogoun *et al.*, 2014). Samples were collected from the trunk or branches. Samples were placed in labelled envelopes and taken to the laboratory for isolation. The machete used to collect the samples was disinfected with 70% alcohol after each sampling.

2.3.2. Data collection

In each of the plantations visited, the feet and branches of the trees were observed to identify symptoms of gum disease. Symptomatic cashew trees were first counted and then marked to avoid double counting.

The health assessment focused on incidence and severity. Disease incidence was determined using the following formula : $I = \frac{\text{Number of trees attacked}}{\text{Total number of trees assessed}} \times 100$ Suresh *et al.* (2017).

Severity was assessed using the method of Cardoso *et al.* (2004). Assessment was based on a rating scale ranging from zero to four, with 0 = no symptoms; 1 = small crack with no gum exudation; 2 = large crack with little or no gum exudation; 3 = crack reaching more than 1/3 of the trunk circumference with abundant gum exudation; 4 = crack completely girdling the trunk or branches with widespread blackening and gum exudation Mekonen *et al.* (2015). The average gum disease severity index (SI) was determined for each of the plantations visited using the following formula : $IS = \frac{\sum (x_i.n_i)}{N.Z} \times 100$

IS : Severity Index ; x_i : score or index on the severity scale ranging from 0 to 4 ; n_i : number of trees of severity i ; N : total number of trees observed; Z: highest score of the assessment (Kranz, 1988).

2.3.3. Isolation and morphological characterization of the gummosis pathogen

For isolation, explants about 5 mm in diameter were taken so as to obtain an explant consisting of both a healthy and a necrotic part. Explants were aseptically treated with 70% ethanol for 1 minute, then with 3% sodium hypochlorite for 2 minutes ; followed by rinsing with sterile distilled water twice for 3 minutes. Explants wrung out on sterile blotting paper were aseptically deposited in Petri dishes containing PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) medium (Silué *et al.*, 2017). The PDA medium was amended with 0.25 g chloramphenicol. Petri dishes were labeled and sealed with stretch film. To promote mycelial growth, Petri dishes were incubated at laboratory temperature (25-28°C) (Dembélé *et al.*, 2020). To obtain pure fungal cultures, fungal mycelia were transferred to the center of new Petri dishes two to three days after incubation. These new dishes were incubated at the same temperature in the laboratory. The fungal isolates obtained from the gummosis samples were first identified macroscopically on the basis of their morphological characteristics, then microscopically in accordance with the determination key of Barnett & Hunter (1972).

2.3.4. Statistical analysis

Plantation data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using STATISTICA version 7.1 software. When a significant difference was observed between the mean values, Fisher's statistical test, at the 5% threshold, was used to separate them.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Symptoms of cashew gummosis in Côte d'Ivoire

Plantations were surveyed during the dry season. The disease starts with a crack on trunks and branches, followed by a brown gum discharge which blackens on contact with light. Severely attacked trees eventually dry out (Figure 2).

Figure 2 : Symptoms of gummosis observed in cashew groves

a: Vertical crack on the trunk; **b:** Abundant gum flow on the trunk; **c:** Brown discoloration under the bark; **d:** Withering of the tree with total defoliation of the crown.

3.2 Incidence of gum blight in different cashew orchards in Côte d'Ivoire

The values obtained after assessing the incidence of gum blight vary from one orchard to another, and therefore from one region to another. These values are presented in Table 1. They range from 5.33% to 48.33% in the regions visited. The incidence values obtained can be grouped into 4 classes (Figure 3). The localities most affected by the disease are Sambadougou (57%), Tiémé (59%), Kolia (60%), and Kasséré (60%), located respectively in the Folon, Kabadougou and Bagoué regions. The least affected localities are Gobazra (3%), Bonon (4%) and Bonoufla (3%). These localities are located in the Marahoué and Haut-Sassandra regions respectively.

Table 1 : Average incidence of gummosis in regions visited

Régions	Incidences (Moyennes ± Écart type %)
Indénié-Djuablin	10,00 ± 2,64 ^{ab}
Bélier	6,66 ± 1,52 ^{ab}
Gbêkê	11,00 ± 5,19 ^{ab}
Haut-Sassandra	11,33 ± 2,51 ^{ab}
Marahoué	5,33 ± 0,57 ^a
Gontougo	15,66 ± 9,66 ^{abc}
Hambol	12,00 ± 5,56 ^{ab}
Béré	8,66 ± 3,78 ^{ab}
Worodougou	22,00 ± 3,60 ^{bc}
Bafing	13,00 ± 5,29 ^{ab}
Folon	43,66 ± 14,64 ^{de}
Kabadougou	45,33 ± 17,21 ^{de}
Bagoué	48,33 ± 16,07 ^e
Poro	31,00 ± 17,08 ^{cd}
Tchologo	16,00 ± 1,52 ^{abc}
Bounkani	16,00 ± 10,53 ^{abc}

Incidence means marked with the same letters are not significantly different according to the Fisher test at the 5% significance level. F = 6.19; P = 0.00

Figure 3: Distribution of gummosis incidence in the regions visited

3.4. Severity of gum blight in different cashew orchards in Côte d'Ivoire

Like incidence, gummosis severity varied from one region to another. The results obtained are presented in Table 2. It ranged from 5.33% to 26.13% in the different regions visited. The severity values can be divided into 5 classes (Figure 4). The most severely attacked localities are Tiémé (33%), Sambadougou (35.66%) and Kolia (35.66%). Gobazra, Petit zuénoula and Bonoufla are the least severely affected, with rates of 3% and 4% respectively.

Table 2: Average severity of gummosis in the regions visited

Régions	Sévérités (Moyennes ± Écart type %)
Indénié-Djuablin	6,77 ± 0,38 ^{ab}
Bélier	5,33 ± 1,25 ^a
Gbêkê	7,72 ± 2,65 ^{ab}
Haut-Sassandra	8,83 ± 2,36 ^{ab}
Marahoué	4,41 ± 0,38 ^a
Gontougo	9,41 ± 8,51 ^{ab}
Hambol	6,66 ± 0,57 ^{ab}
Béré	9,94 ± 1,20 ^{abc}
Worodougou	12,88 ± 3,50 ^{abc}
Bafing	7,94 ± 3,24 ^{ab}
Folon	24,97 ± 10,03 ^{de}
Kabadougou	20,58 ± 11,51 ^{cde}
Bagoué	26,13 ± 9,33 ^e
Poros	15,83 ± 9,88 ^{bcd}
Tchologo	8,33 ± 1,44 ^{ab}
Bounkani	8,27 ± 5,52 ^{ab}

Means of the severity index assigned the same letters are not significantly different according to Fisher's test at the 5% significance level. F = 4.07; P = 0.00

Figure 4: Distribution of gummosis severity in orchards visited

3.5. Morphological characterization of fungal pathogens

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The pathogens isolated from gum blight samples of different origins in Côte d'Ivoire can be classified on the basis of macroscopic and microscopic observations into three genera: *Pestalotia*, *Ceratocystis* and *Lasiodiplodia*.

- *Pestalotia*

On pure growing cultures, the mycelium is aureole-shaped (concentric circle) with a whitish coloration. Over time, black dots (acervuli) spread across the surface of the culture. Fusiform spores are three-celled, brown in color; their upper end is extended by a tandem of single filaments, and the other, more elongated end is transparent and terminates in a single filament (Figure 5).

Figure 5 : Cultural and microscopic characteristics of *Pestalotia* sp.

a, c : upper sides; **b, d :** lower sides; **e :** microscopic observation

- *Ceratocystis*

Ceratocystis isolates were initially yellow in culture, with colorless tips. As they grew, the mycelium changed to a blackish color. Spores are hyaline, elongated and thin-walled (Figure 6).

Figure 6 : Cultural and microscopic characteristics of *Ceratocystis* sp.

a, c : upper surfaces ; **b, d :** lower surfaces; **e :** microscopic observation

- *Lasiodiplodia*

In culture, the cottony-white mycelium spreads rapidly and begins to blacken after filling the Petri dish. Under the microscope, the mycelial filaments are branched and septate. Immature spores are unicellular, ellipsoidal, hyaline and thick-walled, with granular contents. Mature spores are two-celled, dark brown and longitudinally striated (Figure 7).

Figure 7 : Cultural and microscopic characteristics of *Lasiodiplodia* sp.

a, c : upper sides; **b, d :** lower sides; **e, f :** microscopic observations

4. DISCUSSION

Sixteen of the nineteen cashew-producing regions were visited. During the various surveys gummosis was identified in all these regions, which is an indicator of the epidemic nature of the disease and the threat it poses to the industry. However, infection levels varied from one region to another. Disease incidence ranged from 5.33% to 48.33% in all regions surveyed. Severity ranged from 5.33% to 26.13%. ZAE VI regions are the most affected by the disease. This agro-ecological zone is characterized by low rainfall. The low rainfall recorded in the said zone could be one of the factors favoring the high incidence and severity of the disease in this part of the country. Our results corroborate those of Khanza *et al.* (2004), who found in their work that gum blight was more damaging in areas of high water stress than in areas with high rainfall. Cardoso *et al.* (2004) also asserted that lack of water is a determining factor in the expression and development of the disease. This would be due to the weakening of the host caused by this situation. According to Dinis *et al.* (2022), abiotic stress can lead to a reduction in host resistance, making the host vulnerable to the pathogen. In addition, variations in incidence and severity are linked to the poorly controlled or uncontrolled origin of the seeds used to establish orchards, resulting in the expression of great genotypic and phenotypic variability in cashew groves. This is thought to be at the root of the highly heterogeneous behavior of trees in terms of susceptibility to gummosis. In addition, cattle grazing in cashew plantations is a means of spreading the disease. ZAE VI, which covers all the northern regions of the country, is an area of high cattle activity due to favorable climatic conditions. According to MIRAH (2014), 85% of Ivorian cattle are concentrated in the northern zone, 10% in the center and 5% in the south. In plantations, cashew trees are subject to pressure from cattle, which could be a means of spreading the disease. This pressure causes lesions which are entry points for the pathogen (Boddy, 2001).

In the present study, various fungal pathogens were isolated from gum blight samples. These included the genera *Lasiodiplodia*, *Ceratocystis* and *Pestalotia*. The *Lasiodiplodia* genus was the most common, isolated from gum samples from all regions visited. These results are in line with those of Sha *et al.* (2021), and Azuara & Monteon (2021) who, in the course of their work, were able to associate only *Lasiodiplodia* species with gummosis. The other two genera were occasionally isolated, but at very low frequencies. As in this study, the genus *Ceratocystis* has also been associated with gummosis of *Acacia mearnsii* in South Africa (Morris *et al.*, 1993). This is the very first time that a fungus belonging to the genus *Pestalotia* has been associated with gummosis. This could be due to a new strain of the fungus. Indeed, according to Nasraoui (2015), genetic recombination is a factor that enables the formation of new genotypes in fungi.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study has made it possible to update the distribution of gummosis through the assessment of incidence and severity in different agro-ecological zones. It has highlighted the epidemic nature of the disease, as well as the agro-ecological zone in which it occurs. It also identified various fungi belonging to the *Pestalotia*, *Ceratocystis* and *Lasiodiplodia* genera as responsible for cashew gummosis. Pathogenicity studies are currently underway to confirm or refute these results. In view of the cashew industry's contribution to the country's economy, strategies to combat the disease are needed.

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